

Comparing publication information in seven citation indexes

Lorena Delgado-Quirós

ldelgado@iesa.csic.es

José Luis Ortega

jortega@iesa.csic.es

Institute for Advanced Social Studies (IESA) **CSIC**
CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS

Joint Research Unit **ITC** Innovación
Transferencia y
Conocimiento
del Ministerio
de Ciencia

Introduction

Recent proliferation of bibliographic scholarly databases

- Hybrid databases:
 - **As citation indexes:** extracting and processing citations bibliometric indicators
 - **As search engines:** No subscription fee to search and retrieve documents
- Fed by third party sources (e.g., Crossref, PubMed, Microsoft Academic)

Challenges: **Integrating data from different sources**

- Duplicated records and versions
- Different data formats, different fields
- Filtering scientific results: excluding news, front pages, indexes, etc.

Objectives

Comparing the metadata quality about research publications in the new academic databases

- Is it possible to quantitatively compare the metadata content of different databases using a third party source (**Crossref**)? And therefore, to value the information richness of these databases?
- Do similarities or discrepancies among databases allows us to delimit different models of databases, with their advantages and limitations?
- Which do databases provide the most metadata and they have a higher completeness rate?

Methods: Selection

Criteria:

- Freely accessible search interface
- A reliable endpoint: REST API, dump files
- Including metrics

Sample: 116k random record from **Crossref** (2014-2018)

- Assignment of DOI
- No selection criteria
- Source for many of the analyzed databases
- Authoritative source: data deposited by publishers

Methods: Data retrieval

Dates: July 2021 (Scilit, Dec. 2022; OpenAlex, Jan. 2023)

Database	endpoint	procedure
Dimensions	app.dimensions.ai/dsl/v2	R script (dimensionsR)
Google Scholar	scholar.google.com	Web scraping (RSelenium)
OpenAlex	api.openalex.org/	Python script
The Lens	api.lens.org/scholarly/search	<i>Ad hoc</i> R script
Microsoft Academic	zenodo.org/record/2628216	dump files
Scilit	app.scilit.net/api/v1/	Python script
Semantic Scholar	api.semanticscholar.org/v1	<i>Ad hoc</i> R script

Methods: metadata info

Database	Pub.	Pub. %	Information about publication metadata
Crossref	116,592	100%	https://github.com/CrossRef/rest-api-doc/blob/master/api_format.md
Dimensions	105,062	90.1%	https://docs.dimensions.ai/dsl/datasource-publications.html
Google Scholar	101,691	87.2%	https://scholar.google.com/
Microsoft Academic	96,336	82.6%	https://web.archive.org/web/20230329104454/https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/academic-services/graph/reference-data-schema
The Lens	116,337 (4,996)	99.9%	https://docs.api.lens.org/response-scholar.html
OpenAlex	115,881	99.4%	https://docs.openalex.org/
Scilit	113,422	97.3%	No public information
Semantic Scholar	92,314	79.2%	https://api.semanticscholar.org/api-docs/graph

Results: Abstracts

Database	field	pub.	pub. %
Crossref	abstract	15,927	13.7%
Dimensions	abstract	73,145	69.6%
Google Scholar		73,899	91.7%
Microsoft Academic			
OpenAlex	abstract_inverted_index	73,899	63.8%
Scilit	abstract	57,300	50.5%
Semantic Scholar	abstract	50,263	54.5%
The Lens	abstract	3,133	62.7%

Google Scholar extracts abstracts and full text (92%)

Publishers do not deposit this information in **Crossref** (14%)

Scilit (51%) and **Semantic Scholar** (55%) show low abstract extraction and processing

Results: External links

External links

- **Google Scholar** (97%), **The Lens** (83%) and **Microsoft Academic** (81%) include the most external links
- **Crossref** also indexes many links (79%) to improve the accessibility

Open Access

- **Google Scholar** finds the most open access papers (52%) because includes open versions
- **Dimensions** (45%), **The Lens** (44%) and **OpenAlex** (43%) identify the most open access publications

Results: Bibliographic info

Dimensions is the databases with the best coverage (100% volume, 92% pages)

OpenAlex includes only 50% of issue, 50% of pages and 62% of volume. This info is not included in the first release of Dec. 2022

Semantic Scholar does not include issue

Results: Document type

20% of publications in **Microsoft Academic** and 58% in **Semantic Scholar** do not have document type

Scilit and **The Lens** show slight variations according to **Crossref** classification. **OpenAlex** reintroduces *paratext* type for non-academic content

Dimensions reduces significantly the document categories, integrating *book-chapter*, *component*, *reference-entry* and *other* into **chapter** category, and *dataset* and *journal-article* into **article**

Dimensions

OpenAlex

Semantic Scholar

Microsoft Academic

Scilit

The Lens

Results: Publication date

80% of publication years in **Google Scholar** coincide with **Crossref**

Scilit (95%) and **Dimensions** (92%) have the best matching with **Crossref**, while **Microsoft Academic** (70%) and **OpenAlex** (73%) have lower matching rates

Semantic Scholar (58%) and **The Lens** (36%) have high proportions of publications without date

Results: Language

Crossref assigns language according to the venues, **Scilit** according to titles and abstracts and **Microsoft Academic** takes the language from the webpage metadata

Poor matching between language from venues (**Crossref**) and from webpages (**Microsoft Academic**)

Results: Identifiers

Semantic Scholar (98%), **OpenAlex** (87%) and **The Lens** (84%) are mainly based on **Microsoft Academic's** data

PubMed is equally used by all the databases

Dimensions is the product that includes the most ISSN

Conclusions I

Comparing databases according to a third source (**Crossref**), reduces coverage biases and improves the direct benchmark between records

Databases based on external sources (**Dimensions, Scilit, The Lens, OpenAlex**) can generate better and more metadata than academic search engines (**Microsoft Academic, Semantic Scholar**) based on extracting information from the Web

However, this integration also produces problems:

- Loss of information:
 - Publication date in **The Lens**
 - Bibliographic info in **OpenAlex**
- Carrying of inherited limitations from the primary sources:
 - **OpenAlex** with the publication dates of **Microsoft Academic**

Conclusions II

Dimensions is the product that provides the greatest number of fields about publications and the highest completeness degree

OpenAlex, **Scilit** and **The Lens** also include a varied range of fields, but they display some integration problems with lack of information and low completeness rates in specific fields

Search engines such as **Semantic Scholar** and **Google Scholar** lack of important fields for identifying and searching publications (document types, some bibliographic info)

Microsoft Academic is the search engine that provide the most publication fields and their completeness rate is high, although it lacks of information on open access status and document type for some publications

Thank you!

Questions...?